

SPORT IS THE MAIN SOCIAL PHENOMENON OF HUMAN CULTURAL LIFE

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Annotation: This article examines sport as the main socio-cultural phenomenon in the life of a modern person, its tasks, properties and historical formation. Its position in the course of human development and in the modern world is determined.

Keywords : sport, physical culture, society, culture, politics, history, social institution.

During the course of evolution, human civilization has been extremely surviving for a long time and was in a state of constant competition between nature and man and, later, between man and man.

With the gradual achievement of economic benefits and the development of science, danger and anxiety were less and less felt, and more and more people needed to realize their native, competitive qualities. Thus, sport was born as a socio-cultural phenomenon, already 4000 years before our era.

According to the definition, sport is a means and method of physical education based on the practice of competitive activity and preparation for it, during which human capabilities are compared and evaluated. Since ancient times, sport has been a catalyst for cultural, historical and scientific events.

Sport really resonates in society with a powerful versatile force. In all countries, the government is trying to instill in its citizens the habit of playing sports, to make sports a national hobby that should unite people around a common goal. It should also be filled with a kind of ideology, people's desire for success, for victory. Thus, football has become a nationally recognized sport in Argentina. Statistical studies show that sport is able to adapt a person to the need to systematize their daily routine, gain a primary understanding of the structure of life and the world, and sport can also manifest itself as a social elevator. It is in sports activities that one can clearly trace the manifestation of such important values for modern society as competition and success.

Sport as a socio-cultural phenomenon contains a number of relevant functions:

— educational — obtaining the knowledge necessary to understand the natural and social processes of functioning of physical culture of society and personality, the ability to use them creatively for personal and professional development;

- applied — improving specific physical fitness and working capacity for work and military service by means of professionally applied physical culture;
- sports — achieving maximum results in your chosen sport; — recreational
- organizing meaningful leisure;
- health and rehabilitation — prevention of exhaustion and regeneration of temporarily lost functional abilities of the body.

Analyzing the factors of personality formation, we can say that sport is one of the main elements of the socio-cultural aspect of human socialization. In particular, as a form of physical activity and a specific educational factor that implements social technology, with a well-organized system of pre-known rules and behaviors.

As a social institution, sport forms certain "professional statuses" in which each person individually has his own place. Sport reproduces certain starting laws of personality formation, connects an individual to social and public organizations, and forms certain social relationships.

The nature of sports can change the inherent structure of the formation of personal traits of a player, which depend on the behavior model that he chooses in the course of social relationships and game situations, which in turn are close to behavioral patterns in real life. Sport as a socio-cultural identifier recreates the game version of culture, preserves and strengthens the mechanisms of a person's socio-cultural life, and forms him as a socially competent person. Sport is a type of active activity, in the process of which the question of the external scale of self-determination and self-affirmation of the individual is also solved. And on this basis, sport penetrates deeply into the subculture as a social institution, forming lifestyles.

Currently, wide horizons are opening up for the practical definition of a person in society. In such conditions, the social institution of sports is reviving and becoming a socially important phenomenon. The modern model of sports gives a person the opportunity to understand the development strategy, feel the real competitive environment and through this prism assess their place in society. Sport as a socio-cultural phenomenon uses certain basic mechanisms of human self-awareness and self-determination, has specific educational opportunities and is a sphere of affirmation and acquisition of cultural and creative meaning of personality.

Thus, sport enriches the moral and physical health of a person, plays an important political, relaxation role and is still one of the most important socio-cultural phenomena in human life.

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